

PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY OF YARN SPINNING FROM SECONDARY RAW MATERIALS USING THE "SIRO" METHOD

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Annotation: In this article, the physical and mechanical properties of yarn obtained from textile, sewing scraps and scraps are determined. "Siro" yarn is produced from recycled fibers obtained from secondary raw materials, sewing scraps, and cobs.

Key words: raw material, recycled, secondary resources, sliver, roving, physico-mechanical properties, quality competitive

Today, the world-wide textile and sewing-knitting industry is a rapidly developing industry. The textile projects that are being implemented and the jobs that are being created can be a clear proof of this. It has been estimated that approximately 92 million tons of textile waste is generated annually globally, and by 2030, more than 134 million tons of textile products could be discarded annually.

The textile industry in the world is becoming a "Zero-output industry" day by day. A pinching machine is used to separate the scum and clots into fibers. First, the clots are dusted and washed if necessary. The analysis of the existing domestic and foreign techniques and technologies of fiber recovery from secondary raw materials shows that the effective use of fiber extraction technology and the development of the field are envisaged. In the expansion of the raw material base, fiber waste and secondary raw materials generated in the textile industry have a great role. Fibers obtained by processing secondary resources are abundant and cheap compared to other fibers. Studying the properties of such fibers and producing a new range of spun yarn for weaving and knitting fabrics is an urgent problem today.

Analyzing the amount of output in the textile industry in our country in recent years, the share of textile production in January-May 2022 was 7.1%, while the physical volume index increased by 118.7%. production volume 1989.6 bln. amounted to soums (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Volume of textile waste in 2020-2022.

While creating a new assortment of woven and knitted fabrics, it is important to improve the quality of the spun yarn and reduce the unevenness in the yarn. The most important task of spinning enterprises is the production of a new range of quality competitive yarn using existing technologies [3]. Accordingly, experiments on the production of yarn spun by the "Siro" method from a mixture of secondary and chemical fibers obtained from sorghum and cobs using secondary raw materials were conducted in the conditions of the educational laboratory of the "Spinning Technology" department at TITLI [4].

Figure 2. Secondary mixed fibers obtained from coir and cobs

The physico-mechanical properties of the secondary raw materials obtained in the study were determined and brought to the desired moisture content with emulsion (Fig. 2). In this work, in order to produce a 30-tex yarn from chemical and secondary mixed fibers, a 5-tex combed skein was obtained by combing the fibers on an AT-202 roller carding machine. In order to increase the smoothness of the combed skein and improve the yarn quality, 6 combed skeins were added to the HSR-1000 brand skein machine to obtain a 5 ktex braided skein [5]. For the production of 30 tex "Siro" yarn, a spinning plan was drawn up for all rough products from the compound preparation department (Table 1). In the Zinser 668 piling machine, 600 tex piles are obtained from

regenerated fiber from sorghum and cobs and 500 tex piles from polyester fiber. A Zinser 350 ring spinning machine produced "Siro" yarn, a mixture of sorghum, cotton and polyester fibers.

Table 1

Spinning plan for obtaining mixed fiber 30 tex "Siro" yarn

t/r	Transitions	Linear density teks/ktexs	Number of additions	The amount of stretch m/min	Number of twists	Productivity kg/hour
Lumps and clots						
1	Combing	5,40	1	-	-	30
2	Sliver	5,45	6	6	-	126
3	Roving	600	1	9	36	0,950
Chemical fiber (polyester)						
1	Combing	4	1	-	-	34
2	Sliver	4	6	6	-	120
3	Roving	500	1	8	28	0,750
4	Spinning	30	2	700	60	0,0190

The physical and mechanical parameters of the spun yarn were studied. The obtained new assortment of spun yarn is intended for the production of woven and knitted fabrics in the textile industry.

Summary. Effectively using the waste of the textile industry, today's urgent environmental problem, i.e. "No-waste technology" is introduced, and it gives weaving and knitting enterprises the opportunity to produce a new assortment of spun yarn.

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